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2nd INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM
K-FORCE 2019

BOOK OF PROCEEDINGS

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Knowledge FOR Resilient soCiEty

UNIVERSITY OF TIRANA, FACULTY OF ECONOMY, DEPARTMENT OF
FINANCE
Tirana, Albania

EPOKA UNIVERSITY, FACULTY OF ARCHITECTURE AND ENGINEERING
Tirana, Albania

UNIVERSITY OF NOVI SAD, FACULTY OF TECHNICAL SCIENCES
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Novi Sad, Serbia

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Knowledge *F*Or Resilient so*CiE*ty

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PREFACE

The Faculty of Economy, University of Tirana, Epoka University in Tirana and the University of Novi Sad, are organizing the Second International Symposium Knowledge For Resilient soCiEty -K-FORCE 2019, within Erasmus + K-FORCE project.

Natural and man-made disasters, including floods, landslides, earthquakes, storm winds, hail, drought, wildfires and building fires, are on the rise in the last decades in the Western Balkans. Human casualties, extensive damages to the urban areas, negative impact on the environment and further weakening of the regional economy are evidence of increasing vulnerability in the region.

Resilient societies are based on knowledge and training, as well as preparedness. Building synchronized regional capacities in higher education, according to regional needs and contemporary trends, is a first step towards building resiliency of our region. In the light of these observations, the K-Force project has contributed in promoting and developing higher education studies in the field of Disaster Risk Management and Fire Safety Engineering.

In line with the overall objectives of the K-FORCE project, this symposium will be dedicated to discussing current issues in education, science and practice in the field of Disaster Risk Management and Fire Safety Engineering. Contributing not only to education, this project has also produced valuable research. The papers included in this collection are some of the outputs of this research. A significant contribution in this book is one student's paper produced by using Student Centered Learning Methodology, a methodology promoted and applied within the K-FORCE new programs of studies. The new knowledge produced following the strong collaboration between project partners will benefit practitioners, scientists and students working or studying in the field of Disaster Risk Management and Fire Safety Engineering.

Editors

ORGANIZERS OF THE SYMPOSIUM

The Faculty of Economy (FE), established in 1952, became part of the University of Tirana (UT) in 1957. At that time, FE offered majors only in two branches: Economics and Accounting. During the years that followed, the Faculty was enlarged, and in 1990 it offered majors in six branches. After 1991, FE was reorganized and restructured radically in form and content. Today, approximately 3000 students are enrolled in Bachelor studies, over 1500 are Master students and approximately 250 are post-graduate students.

Epoka University is an international HE institution located on a smart campus between the international connections and trading crossroads of Dures Port and Rinas Airport in Tirana, the capital of Albania. The University commenced academic activities during the 2007-2008 academic year. All institutional strategies of Epoka University are built on the “Education, Research and Contribution to Society” triangle. Epoka currently offers Bachelor, Master and Doctorate degrees taught in English, in 32 different programs within three faculties: Faculty of Architecture and Engineering, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, and Faculty of Law and Social Sciences.

The Faculty of Technical Sciences in Novi Sad is an institution of higher education and scientific research founded in 1960. Faculty consists of 13 Departments implementing 88 study programs at the undergraduate and postgraduate level. The Department of Civil Engineering and Geodesy offers a comprehensive study programs in the field of civil engineering, geodesy and disaster and fire risk management: Disaster management and Fire Safety B.Sc. Honours and M.Sc. Qualification levels.

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ADAPTION TO CLIMATE CHANGE - COUNTRIES PERSPECTIVE (A COMPARISON BETWEEN SERBIA AND ALBANIA)

Abstract: Since the early 90s the world begun to raise awareness towards a very common risk: climate change. Nowadays, we are witnessing the impact of these adverse effects and moreover undertaking steps to adapt the strategies and mitigate the consequences. All the countries have embraced their own approaches, adapting to their level of exposure to the risk. Some of the most endangered areas are: food, water and health and natural habitat along with their components. The paper will weigh two regional countries, Albania and Serbia, by paralleling their areas of vulnerability and how they choose to confront them. The response of the government politics, society sensibility and economic impacts will be on target as well.

Key words: adaptation index, agriculture, climate change, readiness, vulnerability

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1. INTRODUCTION

From national to local scale, adaptation planning is the most significant tool for all governments in the world, to set adaptation priorities and to define strategy for climate change combat. Assessing countries vulnerability is starting point in adaptation planning and researchers have been developed many vulnerability indices to show vulnerability in different spheres of interest (environment, society, economy). By establishing international methodologies for calculating vulnerability indexes, vulnerability profile of each country can be set and comparable to each other. By comparing countries vulnerability, less prepared countries can learn from countries which readiness to climate change is higher

The Notre Dame-Global Adaptation Index (ND-GAIN) Country Index is a free open-source index that shows a country's current vulnerability to climate disruptions. It brings together over 74 variables to form 45 core indicators to measure vulnerability and readiness of 192 UN countries from 1995 to the present. Vulnerability is composed of 36 indicators. Each component has 12 indicators, crossed with 6 sectors. Readiness is composed of 9 indicators.

For the purpose of this paper two country profile will be analyzed and discussed, Serbian and Albanian profiles. By their position on the ND-GAIN Country Index, Serbia is ranked at 70th place in the world by scoring relatively low vulnerability and high readiness. While on the other hand, Albania occupies the 78th place by being 91st least vulnerable county and 75th most prepared.¹ The level of readiness is in common, while Albania appears to be more vulnerable. Although less vulnerable, both countries still have to face significant adaptation challenges.

By targeting the most critical areas for both countries provided by ND-GAIN indexes, regarding the vulnerability components and the readiness too, this paper will show strategies and level of adaption that these countries have embraced so far.

2. STUDY AREA

Serbia is a landlocked country situated In Southeastern Europe, in the center of Balkan Peninsula, but due to southern region, in terms of geography and climate it is also considered as Mediterranean country. Albania is located in Balkan Peninsula too, bordered by Adriatic and Ionian Sea in the west and crossed by Albanian Alps in the eastern side.

The greatest sector that climate change has already hit in Serbia since 2000. is agriculture, considered to be the backbone of the economy. Agriculture employs 21% of total labor force, and it is accounted to be 12% of GDP and 19.4% of all exports.² Upon these figures one can easily spot the tight bond and high sensitivity that conducts the country's welfare and this sector. It is estimated that in period of 2000-2018. the severe impacts of climate changes have brought a decline in the yields of grains, mainly maize, wheat and sugar beet which can be

¹<https://gain.nd.edu/our-work/country-index/rankings/>

²<https://www.export.gov/article?id=Serbia-Agribusiness>

converted into 4.6 billion dollars of loss for the country. Major shifts in climate change such as severe droughts and unexpected floods have brought damages in different districts of Serbia from 10% (Bačka) to 90% (Nišava). [2] According to studies, more and more extreme weather conditions are expected and accompanied with decreased frequency of precipitation in summer days, warmer winters and an increase in the number of days with extreme temperature in summer and winter. Under these severe condition's agriculture is most affected. Projected reduction in cereal yields and agriculture capacity decline could be existential problem for poor population too.

As mentioned earlier, Serbia and Albania, as two regional countries, share the same natural climate conditions and characteristics. Global warming has caused an increase in 1.5 °C in the temperature of both countries compared to 0.5 °C that used to be 50 years ago. According to the World Bank study, regarding the countries that represented high vulnerability, precipitation in Albania is expected to decline at a minimum of 30 mm and worst scenario reaches up to 90 mm within 40 years.[3] The coastal area of Albanian territory is dangerously targeted by climate changes too. It is estimated that within five or six generations sea level will rise up to one meter which would completely cover the current coast line and even coastal cities like Durres, partial Vlora, Kavaja would disappear. The greatest thing in common that these countries feature is the high dependency on agriculture sector. The contribution of this sector in the GDP of Albania is 22.5% where 24% of the land is arable.³ The dominance of the sector becomes more obvious when figures show over 50% of Albanian population is employed in agriculture.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

a. Adaptation to climate change - Serbia

According to ND-GAIN study, the level of readiness for a country facing these challenges is related to the government, business and social response. Considerable size of arable land of maize, sugar beet, fruits and legumes, which seem to be intolerant toward water deficiency, each year is affected by extreme drought, thus water supply has been the main focus of Government of Serbia so far. Prevention requires measures like irrigation, drainage system along with the adaption of the technology. Today approximately 70.000 ha of land are under irrigation systems and state government are planning to cover up to 85.000 ha in the next decade, which will result in a total of 5% of the whole arable land.[2] The areas that have had received most of the attention are Šumadija, Vojvodina (where almost 80% of all production of the country is agriculture) and Belgrade Region with the cultures of potatoes, berries and vegetables. These figures show great disadvantage if we compare with other developed countries which are capable of irrigating at least 20% of their arable land. Disadvantages are mainly brought by the lack of: economic stability, expertise, and technology.

As for the drainage, according to Water Master Plan, approximately 2.01 million of hectare is covered by drainage and water management system.[4] In the past years of 2014 and 2015 it is shown that minimum of maintenance cost has significantly exceed the capacity of

³<https://www.export.gov/article?id=Albania-Agricultural-Sector>

government to invest, as only 59% of required investment could be fulfilled by the government. The main water management companies in Serbia (Srbijavode, Vode Vojvodine and Beograd Vode) currently require for regular maintenance and investment respectively 8.9 million RSD, 3.5 billion RSD and 2 billion RSD.⁴

The biggest priorities technology-related are: changes in plant species, where one specie's feature combines with the other's so that it the new one can perfectly adapt to the future climate change, introduction to the species more tolerant to severe conditions, creation of new adaptive genotypes and so on. All that require investment, progress tracking and training.

During this present decade Serbia has been an active part of numerous EU regulations, projects and frameworks for the purpose of adapting to the climate changes and mitigating their consequences. The agreement with FAO allowed the launch of farmers' training in different municipalities which seemed to have considerable positive feedback. It is worth mentioning the catastrophic floods that invaded Serbia back in 2014 where the natural disaster found the state especially landowners completely uncovered and vulnerable towards very threatening conditions. Under these adverse circumstances one can easily spot the obstacles that hinder the whole society while trying to adapt and overcome such difficulties.

Nowadays it takes a lot of budget for a low-medium society to invest in innovation which according to ND – GAIN study, appears to be the lowest score on chart. This crucial criterion of Readiness appeared briefly a few lines above where was mentioned the inability of the state to invest in the proper technology that the system of irrigation, drainage, the implementation of newest technology and an ameliorated forecasting is to be done. In the end, as we can understand, it takes the whole incorporation of society and businesses in the terms of raising awareness towards gas emission from fabrics and vehicles where seems like the country finds it difficult to quit.

b. Adaptation to climate change -Albania

According to ND - GAIN Albania showed higher rate of vulnerability than Serbia, due to higher exposure of population in this field. Accompanied with the help and guideline of World Bank and other small financing institutions Albania in 2007 establish an irrigating system for about 180.000 hectare of land and another 120.000 hectare of total drainage and storage water stream. These figures cover respectively 50% and 40% of total arable land in Albania which means that still half of it crucially depends on rainfalls.

As for the productivity under climate change conditions wheat remains the most productive and important in Albania. But as it is seen since '90s, wheat continues to grow at a very slow rate, by only 1.6% each year. In the predicted scenario by World Bank if Albania continues to undertake the same level of measures towards unstoppable climate change events, some substantial shortages in the crop production are expected. Starting by fruits and vegetables, especially tomato and grape, production of each is expected to decline respectively 11% and 20% in the next few decades. Maize, alfalfa and pasture tend to have shortages in 10-25% of production. The impact of these figures becomes more and more severe when we add the fact that three-quarters of families placed in rural areas can make averagely 5\$ per day.

⁴<http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data>

Certain global institutions such as WB and FAO have supported Albania by investing in irrigation systems, increasing the exposure towards new technologies and leading our institutions into a better management of grants that are given to this sector.

According to UN “Map of Food Security and Climate Changes” Albania is the most endangered country in terms of food security by climate changes. According to the study, by the year of 2050 the estimated risk in the terms of food access will rise in 25%, considerably high in compare with other neighbor countries. While speaking for the food safety, the figures appear even more alarming, where almost 48% of food will certainly be unsafe to consume. Climate extreme events will increase the intensity of natural disasters such as floods, drought and storms. This would lead to the complete destruction of yields, infrastructure and bring more poverty in the affected areas. Another argument in disfavor stands behind the fact that currently there are certain cultures endangered because of adverse climate conditions and the lack of supply for these items increases tremendously the price in certain areas of cultivation. This leads to unequal share of goods where low income families have to give up in consuming certain goods and eventually a decrease in the number of the goods in a consumer’ basket.

4. CONCLUSION

If we compare the conditions that both countries are situated we get to realize that amongst everything, the zone with highest vulnerability in Serbia is the high fluctuation on revenues in the exporting of agriculture that climate changes bring, while agriculture capacity remains a problem by the lack of technology, irrigation and drainage system, along with shortages in crop production year after year. This counts as an adverse impact in this crucial sector of economy for the whole Serbian population and the state in general. In Albania, climate changes bring the adverse effect directly to the farmers of the rural area, whose revenues are completely depending on the production, while the conditions get worsened by the high dependency ratio in food import which again falls over poor population.

The level of readiness for both countries remains abstract and far away from figures that show proper level of adaption. Global organizations have helped countries so far by analyzing data, giving funds and then advising countries’ institutions towards a better adaption. Many studies and surveys prepared by academics, environmentalists, statisticians show that most of the people regardless of age, education and social status believe that through proper environment politics and policies in gas emission criteria, water management, agricultural policies, waste management, renewable energy and sustainable solutions it is possible to embrace the first steps towards fighting global warming.

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